

Organisational Performance: Difference in digital resilience in SME and large organisations

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ABSTRACT

Organisational capability is the ability of a firm to perform a coordinated task, utilising organisational resources, to achieve a particular result (O'Regan & Ghobadian, 2004). Process alignment and organisational learning culture significantly contribute to organisational dynamic capabilities and ultimately performance ().

The literature shows organisational capabilities research in the financial tech industry is often based on samples from large financial tech enterprises. There is little research done on small and medium-sized enterprises (SME). However, in the EU economy about 99% of the enterprises are SMEs (European Commission, 2021). In this research the objective of this study is to examine the influence of dynamic capabilities on digital resilience after cyber security failures in SME compared to large enterprises in FinTech services.

Furthermore, SMEs face special challenges because they have fewer options in terms of resources, capabilities, and market power (Dr Nevich & Kriauciūnas, 2011; Sawers, Pretorius, & Oerlemans, 2008). Therefore, dynamic competence is especially critical for SME competition and success because, unlike their larger peers, SMEs may find it challenging to regularly renew their resource base to respond to a changing environment (Wang, Shi, Jones, 2011).

The methods that are going to be conducted for this paper are distinguishable by desk research and field research. Desk research will be applied by examining existing (academic) literature, and applying or examining business models. What models will be used, is dependent on the examined population. Field research will be conducted in the form of semi-structured field-surveys and or

experiments. This means some of the questions asked are determined in advance by the interviewer. The order in which the questions are asked is flexible and the respondents can answer completely freely. This leaves room for gathering extra information that would not be available if a structured method is used. The given results from the desk and field research will indicate a baseline that will help to evaluate the conclusions.

It is expected to provide a clear picture of the findings from desk research. Literature in the field of dynamic capabilities in SME and large enterprises will lead to a good basis for creating a qualitative survey or experiment. This experiment will then have to substantiate or defend the influence of dynamic capabilities after cyber security failures in SME and large enterprises for the enhancement of cyber resilience. Field research can also provide a picture of the dynamic capabilities and influence on cyber resilience. The relevance lies with the process alignment and organisational learning culture. Lastly the relevance of this paper will also be in SME and large enterprises, as it will thrive from the knowledge this paper will accumulate.

Keywords

Process alignment, learning culture, digital resilience, cultural agility, dynamic capabilities, organisational performance

INTRODUCTION

In the highly competitive business environment that characterises the online economy, a focus on innovation and growth leads companies to rush products and services to market, security being merely an afterthought that can be fixed later (Castells, 1996; Weulen Kranenbarg et. al., 2018). In addition, the outbreak of COVID-19 has accelerated this digital transformation (Gabryelzyk, 2020). COVID-19 has affected the reduction of the activities of all humanity, but also the conduct of business activities in the normal conditions to which we have been accustomed so far. Reduced social interaction, social distancing, lockdown, restrictions on movement and restructuring of business are disturbances caused by the pandemic that has significantly transformed our daily lives and set requirements for accepting and getting used to the “new normal” way of life of all humanity. In such social and business conditions, information and communication technologies (ICT) have shown their importance and become crucial for the continuation of personal and business services and interactions (Kutnjak, 2021).

The world of finance, particularly the banking sector, is of undoubted importance to the daily lives of people worldwide. Traditional banking has changed significantly during the last century but, today, a new epoch of financial service, called “FinTech,” has emerged (Zavolokina, Dolata, Schwabe, 2016). The development of information technologies (cloud computing, mobile communications, online social networks) reshaped the business models in the financial industry (Bratasanu, 2019). Firms need to adapt to environmental change to remain successful. When the environment is dynamic or unpredictable, firms are especially challenged to revise their routines (March, 1991). Helfat (1997) suggests that organisational capabilities allow firms to create new products and processes and respond to changing market circumstances.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Metaverse is a form of digital transformation which increased rapidly in popularity. It conceived new opportunities in the field of gaming, recreation, education and trading. Many businesses in the physical world have been making the transmission into the Metaverse, with the main goal to increase its revenue and increase the value of its stock market (Belk & Humayun & Brouard, 2022). But everything has a downside, including this. The transitioning to the digital world also bears the fact that these virtual businesses will more likely be exposed to cybercrime and the associated modus operandi. One of the consequences of this involves

the financial losses of a virtual business after a data breach. Research has shown that cybercrime will only increase in the following years, and with the rise of the Metaverse, it will result in increased risks for virtual businesses in losing financial assets. Cybercrime and different attacking methods, such as data leaks, will continue to persist in the Metaverse, but no research has been done before on how data breach in particular can financially impact the stock market of a ‘physical’ business. This describes the current knowledge gap in this field. This subject is particularly relevant nowadays since many potential organisations are considering moving into the Metaverse, with a risk of being a victim of cybercrime (Belk & Humayun & Brouard, 2022).

Organisations have more customer information than ever before. This information is valuable to the organisation and therefore must be protected from data thieves. According to [Idtheftcenter.org](https://www.idtheftcenter.org) (2022), the number of data compromises (1,862) is up over 68 percent from 2020. As cyberattacks become more sophisticated and complex, organisations are handling their data more defensively. According to the Ponemon Institute the financial industry is after the healthcare industry the most hacked industry. Larger firms have a greater variety of options than small firms in terms of resources, capabilities and power, although their activities, too, are constrained by personal and institutional factors. Innovative small firms are generally characterised as being flexible and having the ability to respond faster to changing needs and environments (Sawers, Pretorius, Oerlemans, 2008). With weaker market power and high vulnerability to external pressures and environmental changes, the most critical factors for small and medium enterprises (SME) success are to maintain flexibility and adapt to a changing environment (Wade & Hulland, 2004; Wang et al., 2011). Requirements for SMEs are staff count lower than 250, turnover under 50 million or balance sheet total under 43 million (European commission, 2003). Although extensive studies have been conducted on the outcomes of organisational learning culture and organisational process alignment, most management literature stresses the benefits of organisational learning culture and organisational process alignment separately (Hung, Yang, Lien, McLean, Kuo, 2010). This is why the study of Hung, Yang, Lien, McLean, Kuo, 2010 examined the inter-relationship between organisational learning culture and process alignment and their joint influence on organisational performance in cyber resilience after cyber security failures from a dynamic capability perspective. The limitation of

this study was the fact that the study sample was composed of large homogenous high-tech enterprises.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The purpose of our study is to examine the dynamic capabilities of SMEs compared to large enterprises in FinTech after cybersecurity failures. Therefore, we have formulated the following research question:

What influence does dynamic capabilities have on digital resilience in small enterprises compared to large enterprises in FinTech after cyber security failures?

Sample and procedure

This study uses a survey research methodology to examine the hypothesised relationship among organisational process alignment, organisational learning culture, dynamic capabilities and cyber resilience. The sampling frame consists of 5 SMEs and 3 large enterprises in the Netherlands. Samples for the study were collected from the connection of the researchers. The most appropriate informants for this study are managers. The managers of these enterprises will receive a questionnaire in their mail. To encourage respondents to complete and return the questionnaires follow-up calls and mails will be sent. A total of 8 responded. The responses were divided into SMEs and large enterprises. Every response was usable and analysed.

METHODS

In this section the approach of this research will be explained. This will be followed with the results where the key findings of the relevant papers are stated. To collect information, field research and desk research have been used as the main methods of information provision. By applying field research, new information will be created for this research whether by applying desk research, existing information and knowledge have been used.

This research started off by choosing a general topic which in this case is the cultural adaption of organisations in cyber security. Several articles are analysed by scanning these articles on useful information to define our knowledge gap. The knowledge gap will be identified by analysing whether there are any elements in common, any differences or the articles contradict each other. By using desk research, we hoped to define a knowledge gap that will encourage other

researchers to further research this subject. The key findings from these articles are stated in the section results, if necessary, quotes are used to convey information. In the process, there was a knowledge gap found within the area of dynamic capabilities of SME compared to large FinTech organisations and the influence of this dynamic capabilities after cyber security failures on digital resilience.

Conceptual framework

figure 1

The basic conceptual framework shown in figure 1 illustrates the inter-relationship between dynamic capability and its antecedent and outcome variables. The model is divided into two groups: SME and large enterprises. These two variables both have an independent influence on cyber resilience. This model further includes organisational performance on digital resilience as the endogenous variable. Beside that there are two exogenous variables: organisational learning culture and process alignment. Lastly there is a mediating variable known as dynamic capabilities. The proposed model posits that process alignment and organisational learning culture in SME or large enterprises are inter-related and are the antecedents of dynamic capability and organisational performance on cyber resilience.

Survey

The aim of this study is to find out what influence cultural agility has on digital resilience after cyber security failures within large and small enterprises. To make this measurable there is used a survey with questions on a Likert scale about various topics within the research subject. The questions of the survey are compiled based on scientific theory. The exact questions that are used can be found in the appendix. The results of the survey are opinions of employees with different positions within small and large enterprises in the financial and technology sector.

The 5-point Likert scale data will be exported to SPSS for analysis purposes. The validity and reliability of the results will be tested by a

regression analysis. Furthermore the interpretation of the output will be done based on the mean and standard deviation. Beside the mean and standard deviation there will be also looked at the Cronbach alpha of the question results. This is to ensure internal consistency. Besides the statistical analysis, the questions are analysed by the distribution of the answers. In the figure below, the Chronbach alpha output is explained.

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

figure 2

Different biases

Observation bias has been reduced through anonymous testing. Confirmation bias by testing substantial correlation by testing for Cronbach alpha. Response rate issues are created because of the lack of responses. This makes the results less reliable. Random response bias has been meet by formulating the survey questions clearly

THEORY

Digital resilience gets supported by the process alignment and the dynamic capabilities. The article of Hung, et al. (2010) states that the effect on organisational performance has a positive correlation with process alignment and dynamic capabilities that are divided with yet again process alignment and the learning culture as well. The variable organisational performance is more comprehensive than digital resilience. This paper zooms in on digital resilience after cyber security failures.

Process alignment

Previous studies have confirmed that organisational process alignment positively influences performance. Specifically, Ostroff (1999) proposed that the effectiveness of organisational performance increases with the degree of horizontalness of organisational structure. Benner and Tushman (2003) suggest that organisational innovation and adaptation depend on appropriate structure alignment between process management and environment. Strategic alignment is also positively related to organisational performance (Hinterhuber, 1995; Lee & Dale, 1998; Zairi, 1997). Further, strategic alignment of internal firms

promotes a more dynamic platform and enhances strategic capabilities. We propose that dynamic capability partially mediates the effect of process alignment on organisational performance. Both theories and existing empirical evidence support the notion that a firm's dynamic capability can be enhanced by process alignment. In sum, the literature suggests that organisational process alignment, namely structure alignment, strategic alignment, and IT alignment, is an antecedent to organisational performance and dynamic capability. Thus, the following hypotheses are proposed: Hypothesis 1. Organisational process alignment is positively related to organisational performance. Hypothesis 2. Organisational process alignment is positively associated with dynamic capability.

Learning culture

Although the terms 'organisational learning' and 'learning organisation' are used somewhat interchangeably in the literature, they are different concepts. Preskill and Torres (1999) stated that the term 'learning organisation' focuses on the systems, principles and characteristics of an organisation that learns as a collective, while 'organisational learning' focuses on the actual process of how organisational learning happens. Learning organisation generally describes specific characteristics of an ideal organisation, while organisational learning describes processes or activities related to organisational change. For this paper the organisational learning culture using the Dimensions of Learning Organization Questionnaire (DLOQ) designed by Watkins and Marsick (1993, 2003) was used. Same to Wang et al.'s study (2007), organisational learning culture was assessed on a six-point Likert-type scale. Respondents are asked to determine the degree to which each of the questions reflects their organisations' situations in learning culture (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). According to the suggestion of the authors of the instrument, this study assessed perceived organisational learning culture at the individual, team/group, and organisational levels.

Dynamic capabilities

Eleven Items are adopted from Bierly & Chakrabarti (1996) and Danneels (2002) to assess organisational dynamic adaptation. Four out of seven items relate to organisational strategic capability, three items have been used to measure innovative capability, and the last four items are assessed to organisational management capabilities.

Digital resilience

Digital resilience will be measured through organisational performances. The assumption is made that organisational performances will accumulate cyber resilience in a crisis situation. Organisational performances are dependent on the process alignment and the learning culture but also gets measured in the survey. The organisational performances are measured with 5 items from Keskin (2006), Lawler, Mohrman, and Ledford (1998) and Powell (1995). The respondents are asked to compare the capabilities of their firm with major competitors. The correspondent focuses on relative company advantages because of the comparison with a competitive firm. To control the correlation between organisational performances and digital resilience, additional questions regarding cyber resilience have been conducted in the survey.

To test this hypothesis field research has been applied in the form of a survey to test the possible differences. Given the available time, a structured questionnaire has been used to make a difference between primary and secondary data.

RESULTS

What influence does cultural agility have on digital resilience in small enterprises compared to large enterprises after cyber security failures?

To analyse the data, for every subset the mean has been calculated. The significance(Sig.) of the variables differ greatly. The regression model fits the data well, as the Sig. of model fitting information is .000 and the goodness of fit is Sig. 1.000. The log likelihood is practically zero. This means that no comparison can be made between the different subsets.

Cultural agility

Cultural agility can be described as the ability to adapt to changes made in the organisation and is linked to organisational culture as agile behaviour gets stimulated by the culture of an organisation. Cultural adaptation as described in (Moon, 2010) is stimulated by the capacity of the organisation to be dynamic. “Consistent with the dynamic capabilities view, firms can develop the capability to adapt their resources and competencies to cross-cultural environments by facilitating the learning process with coordinating and restructuring resources, build-ing on their positions and assets in the foreign market, and paths they have travelled” (Moon, 2010). To improve the digital resilience of cyber security attacks, a dynamic organisational structure is

preferred. Hung, et al. (2010) states that dynamic capabilities in organisations rely on the creation of an organisational learning culture and the process alignment of an organisation. Where the learning culture has a greater impact on dynamic capabilities than the process alignment (Hung, et al., 2010). The performance of an organisation is dependent on the dynamic capabilities so that means that cultural agility is important for better organisational performances. The difference between small to medium enterprises and large enterprises can be found in the learning culture and the process alignment of the organisations. The difference in resilience can be explained by those factors.

The survey data clearly shows that there is very little difference between small and large enterprises in cultural agility.

CA	MEAN	Stand. er.	Stand. dv.
Small enterprise	3,9	0,30259	0,6767
Large enterprise	3,9	0,26021	0,15023

Figure 3

Learning culture

Learning and knowledge management are crucial capacities for many organisations. In order for an organisation to be able to drive the desire to learn it needs to be agile. (John Hailey & Rick James,2002). Although organisations learn in different ways, with some emphasising informal methods and others more formal approaches, what is common to all is their fundamental commitment to learning. Learning is one of their core values and pervades their organisational culture. Thus, learning is not just a resource or asset to be invested in, it is also a crucial part of the values and culture of the organisation. Learning should be a key characteristic of the organisational culture in order to motivate staff. (John Hailey & Rick James,2002). Viewing this from a cyber security perspective, creating a positive learning environment should increase the amount of curiosity and willingness to learn more about this topic which should determine the digital resilience of an organisation.

The survey data shows a small difference in learning culture between small and large enterprises where smaller companies have a higher score over large companies.

LC	MEAN	Stand. er.	Stand. dv.
Small enterprise	4,0	0,090	0,190
Large enterprise	3,9	0,100	0,173

Figure 4

Process alignment

Process alignment refers to the arrangement of various parts in a company that work together to pursue common organisational goals (Weiser, 2000). Whether the organisation is a small or large enterprise it must design its structures and systems to align the contingencies of environment, strategy, and technology for survival and success (Anand & Daft, 2007). What also is a part of survival is how companies react after cyber security failures. Within the process alignment there also should be given attention to cultural agility regarding cyber security. Most importantly to include is the adoption and use of the measures that have to accompany threats and risks. These most commonly relate to the implementation of information and cyber security. Developing standards influences cultural adaptation and will have an impact on the awareness of cyber security. Comprehensive information security solutions involve multifaceted physical, procedural and logical forms of protection for the information in question. This type of security is typically implemented in an organisational context (R. M. Ahlfeldt, P. Spagnoletti & G. Sindre, 2007).

The survey data shows a difference in small and large enterprises where large enterprises score higher on process alignment then small enterprises.

PA	MEAN	Stand. er.	Stand. dv.
Small enterprise	3,6	0,167	0,37546

Large enterprise	3,8	0,135	0,23353
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Figure 5

Organisational performance

Organisational performance is the ability to attain goals by using resources in an efficient and effective manner according to Daft (2000).

Organisational performance has been the most important issue for every organisation be it profit or non-profit one. It has been very important for managers to know which factors influence the organisation's performance in order for them to take appropriate steps to initiate them. The organisational performance construct was measured using 5 items adapted from Keskin (2006). The construct includes (1) competitive advantage, (2) market share, (3) customer satisfaction, (4) data awareness, (5) profit. The assumption is made that organisational performance will accumulate cyber resilience.

The results on organisational performances are distinguished in 2 categories. The operational performances and the expected recovery of the company after a cyber security failure. Organisational performances are rated lower at larger enterprises but the cyber resilience is rated higher than small organisations.

OP	MEAN	Stand. er.	Stand. dv.
Small enterprise	3,3	0,2332	0,52154
Large enterprise	3,1	0,2905	0,23353
CR			
Small enterprise	3,6	0,678	1,517
Large enterprise	3,7	0,882	1,528

Figure 6

Cronbach alpha

With the use of Cronbach Alpha the reliability can be measured across multiple domains. For this study, the results of 4 domains have been analysed through SPSS in order to calculate Cronbach Alpha. The results are as follows:

Process alignment

This study assessed organisational process alignment using 15 items. The assessment scale measures the integration between the process alignment, IT alignment and the Strategic alignment. These three domains: Process alignment with 5 items, IT alignment with 4 items, and strategic alignment with 6 items to measure. Appendix A describes the measurement items.

To measure the given answers a Likert-type scale has been used where the reliability is calculated with Cronbach's alpha. the overall reliability estimate for the scale is .220

Organisational learning culture

This study assessed organisational process alignment using 17 items. The assessment scale measures the integration between the Individual level, Team or group level and the Organisational level. These three domains: Individual level with 5 items, Team or group level with 6 items, and Organisational level with 6 items to measure. Appendix A describes the measurement items.

To measure the given answers a Likert-type scale has been used where the reliability is calculated with Cronbach's alpha. the overall reliability estimate for the scale is .278

Organisational dynamic capability

This study assessed organisational process alignment using 11 items. The assessment scale measures the integration between the Organisational strategic capability, Organisational management capability. These three domains: Organisational strategic capability with 4 items, R&D innovative capability with 3 items, and Organisational management capability with 4 items to measure. Appendix A describes the measurement items.

To measure the given answers a Likert-type scale has been used where the reliability is calculated with Cronbach's alpha. the overall reliability estimate for the scale is .749

Organisational performance

This study assessed organisational process alignment using 5 items. The assessment scale measures the Organisational performance Appendix A describes the measurement items.

To measure the given answers a Likert-type scale has been used where the reliability is calculated with Cronbach's alpha. the overall reliability estimate for the scale is -.008

In the two sectors of Process alignment and Organisational learning culture the results are very inconsistent resulting in a lower score.

Organisational dynamic capability has shown an average score and can be deemed as consistent. Organisational performance has also shown to be very inconsistent resulting in a lower score.

CONCLUSION

A significant difference between small and large enterprises in digital resilience after cyber security failures can not be proven. The organisational performances are rated worse for large enterprises but still the cyber resilience has been rated higher. The effect of process alignment could be the explanation, because the process alignment has a direct impact on organisational performances.

The process alignment is rated higher in large companies. This could explain why large enterprises would respond faster to breaches. The processes are already made and automated, unlike small firms, where less processes are aligned. This can lead to slower responses when security breaches occur.

Cultural agility is rated evenly by the big and small firms, which tells us that both small and large firms both experience dynamic capabilities. Both firm sizes achieve the capability to adjust with a dynamic view. Resources and competencies of cross-cultural environments are facilitated by learning processes in the organisation which leads to the last subject.

The learning culture in both large and small firms are not very different. Big and small firms both seem to provide a culture where learning is stimulated and employees get the opportunity to accelerate their knowledge with learning opportunities.

The Cronbach alpha is lower than expected. The main reason for this is the low sample size. The expectation is that the variance will decrease when more organisations are interviewed.

Managerial implications

The research highlights that the process alignment is higher in large organisations. Digital resilience after cyber security failures in SMEs can be improved by focusing on process alignment. The various parts such as environment, strategy, and technology should be aligned. Developing policies in SMEs influences cultural adaptation and will have a positive impact on the awareness of cyber security.

Limitations and future research

First off, the findings are based on a low sample size. The reason for this is that there was not enough time to carry out a large survey.

Furthermore the sample size consists of organisations settled in the Netherlands, which is not a representative sample for the organisations worldwide. Further research could replicate the experimental approach proposed in this study, while focusing on a bigger and internationally sample of this research.

Another limitation that could be captured is the lack of homogeneity in the research sample. Fintech has different categories of organisations. For example banking, payments, lending and personal financial management. Banks are more often victims of cyber crime. The assumption is that fintech banking organisations therefore have better standards than personal financial management organisations.

Appendix A. Survey Questions

Appendix 1	Scale
<p>1. Size of company by number of employees</p> <p>2. Process alignment likert scale (1) Horizontal structure alignment a. High barriers between departments (R). b. Frequent use of process teams. c. Cross-functional teams have more authority in making day-to-day decisions than departmental managers. d. Customer satisfied with response time. e. Managerial tasks to front-line staff delegated.</p> <p>(2) IT alignment a. Technology enabled business processes to perform well. b. State-of-the-art technology. c. IT important to improvement of business processes. d. Well integrated IT systems across functional units.</p> <p>(3) Strategic alignment a. Developed strategies based on customer needs. b. Core processes important input into strategic plan. c. Operational improvements had direct impact on ability to compete. d. Sufficient measures permit clear tracking of performance. e. Current strategic plan identified actually undertaken. f. Strategic planning process actually encourages information sharing and cross-functional cooperation (Hung et al, 2010).</p>	<p>Nominal</p> <p>5p likert scale</p>
<p>3. Organizational learning culture (1) Individual level a. In my organization, people identify skills they need for future work tasks. b. In my organization, people are rewarded for learning. c. In my organization, people give open and honest feedback to each other. d. In my organization, people listen to others' views before speaking. e. In my organization, people spend time building trust with each other.</p> <p>(2) Team or group level a. In my organization, teams/groups have the freedom to adapt their goals as needed. b. In my organization, teams/groups treat members as equals, regardless of rank, culture, or other differences. c. In my organization, teams/groups focus both on the group's task and on how well the group is working. d. In my organization, teams/groups revise their thinking as a result of group discussions or information collected. e. In my organization, teams/groups are rewarded for their achievements as a team/group (Hung et al, 2010).</p> <p>(3) Organizational level a. My organization makes its lessons learned available to all employees. b. My organization gives people choices in their work assignments. c. My organization gives people control over the resources they need to accomplish their work. d. My organization encourages people to get answers from across the organization when solving problems. e. In my organization, leaders generally support requests for learning opportunities and training. f. In my organization, leaders mentor and coach those they lead.</p>	<p>5p likert scale</p>

<p>4. Organizational dynamic capability</p> <p>(1) Organizational strategic capability</p> <p>a. My organization owns future competitive flexibility in industry.</p> <p>b. My organization owns ability that can fast aware new business opportunity or threat possibility.</p> <p>c. In my organization, leaders have entrepreneurship characteristics.</p> <p>d. My organization has the ability to cohesive employees' knowledge by visioning.</p> <p>(2) R&D innovative capability</p> <p>a. My organization has the ability to evaluate my own organization's strength and weakness.</p> <p>b. My organization has the ability to know the direction and timing for R&D.</p> <p>c. My organization has the flexibility to development new product or technology.</p> <p>(3) Organizational management capability</p> <p>a. My organization has the flexibility to understand the specific needs of customers.</p> <p>b. My organization has the flexibility to communicate and coordinate effectively among departments.</p> <p>c. My organization helps employees to balance the life of work and family.</p> <p>d. My organization coordinates with community to fulfil mutual needs (Hung et al, 2010).</p>	<p>5p likert scale</p>
<p>5. Organizational performance</p> <p>(1) During the past three years, change in competitive advantage relative to your largest competitor has markedly improved.</p> <p>(2) During the past three years, change in market share relative to your largest competitor has markedly improved.</p> <p>(3) During the past three years, change in customer satisfaction</p> <p>(4) During the past three years, the company has become more secure with employee data (Hung et al, 2010).</p> <p>(5) Covid had a big influence on the profitability.</p>	<p>5p likert scale</p>
<p>6. Cyber resilience</p> <p>(1) Historic security failures in the company.</p> <p>(2) (Expected) recovery time after a security failure.</p>	<p>5p likert scale</p>

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